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of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

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An elegy for an old friend

Standing where flowers
Are already wilting,
Coffin is closed
Like chances I never opened.

Holding apologies sound too loud
In a place answers with soil.
I mistook your silence for strength,
While standing beside another life.

If time bent backward,
I would sit beside you in dark,
Listen to words
You buried inside.

But wind finishes prayer
Before I arrive.
Shadow doesn't reach graves
And it learns too late what distance costs.

Old friend,
I was not there
When they lowered you down.
Boundaries kept me standing far,
Knees shaking,
Hands empty.
Now I speak to a space
That will never answer.